

When Metadata Isn't Enough: Extrinsic Quality Assessment of OSM Tags Using Custom Reference Data

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OpenStreetMap is a notable example of a database created by volunteers. Due to its open approach to data collection, establishing trust in the data is essential. Three key factors must be considered to evaluate this trust: completeness, correctness, and positional accuracy. The most common method in recent years for assessing large datasets like OpenStreetMap is to examine intrinsic data quality [1-3], which relies on metadata. However, this approach does not allow for a thorough analysis of the mapped features, resulting in only a rough estimate of the data's trustworthiness. To provide a more detailed understanding of the data, extrinsic data quality is evaluated by comparing OpenStreetMap with a reference dataset. This method is effective for evaluating feature completeness. However, when assessing attribute accuracy, a similarly detailed dataset for comparison is often unavailable. In these instances, the evaluator must gather their own reference dataset, which can be expensive and time-consuming. Because of that, previous studies and tools mainly focused on assessing attribute accuracy by utilizing intrinsic data quality [2, 4, 5].

In our study, we focused on assessing the extrinsic data quality of the city of Brno in the Czech Republic. We wanted to know how much we can trust OpenStreetMap tags (hereinafter referenced as attributes) in our city, and if there is some correlation between attribute accuracy and metadata of the features. A secondary objective was to determine how well ISO 19157 [6] can be used to assess the attribute quality of the OpenStreetMap. We chose the city's ten most mapped amenity features and gathered a reference dataset for these features. Since we knew what we would be evaluating, we have acquired a dataset perfect for evaluating OpenStreetMap. Thus, there was no need for major compromises in data evaluation. Over the course of several months, we traveled more than 1,000 km on foot and gathered a few thousand reference features using the Locus GIS app. Each feature contained a list of evaluated attributes together with a photo of the object for further evaluation. Evaluated amenities were *bench*, *waste_basket*, *recycling*, *restaurant*, *bicycle_parking*, *cafe*, *vending_machine*, *post_box*, *pub* and *fast_food* – the most mapped node features in Brno. The OpenStreetMap database was evaluated as of September 27, 2023.

Our assessment of OpenStreetMap's attribute accuracy revealed generally positive results. Several attributes in our sample achieved 100% accuracy, particularly those with boolean values. However, the most significant issues arose with string attributes that lack

defined value lists, such as *opening_hours*. Ultimately, the primary concern identified was the completeness of the data. We found that the completeness of feature occurrence is inadequate; we were only able to match 34.94% of all reference features with those in OpenStreetMap. This completeness varied significantly across evaluated amenities, with *waste_baskets* and *benches* being notably underrepresented. Incompleteness also affects the usability of attributes. Of the 72 tags evaluated, only 37 tags had at least 50% of their values filled in, and only 11 tags had over 90% of their values filled in.

We also assessed the positional accuracy of the data. Each amenity was evaluated separately, revealing average positional errors ranging from 2.63 meters to 4.02 meters. The median error was found to be between 1.83 meters and 3.13 meters. Overall, OpenStreetMap appears to be a relatively accurate positional database for the city of Brno, despite some isolated deviations (outliers).

When examining the relationship between attribute accuracy and feature metadata, we assumed that more users editing a feature would lead to more accurate data. This concept is known as the “many eyes principle” [7, 8]. However, the correlations between metadata (such as the number of contributors, versions, and days since the last edit) and attribute correctness are typically not statistically significant. As a result, no explicit dependency can be determined, and no clear patterns emerge from a few statistically significant values.

Our work also shows that evaluating OpenStreetMap using ISO 19157 [6] can be problematic because this standard does not consider multiple correct values or the varying degrees of attribute correctness (“level of detail” of attributes). Additionally, automating the evaluation of specific attributes, such as *opening_hours*, is challenging since these attributes can contain different yet correct values. Moreover, missing or incomplete documentation can significantly impact evaluations, as there should be clear rules specifying which values are considered correct. This presents a challenge for projects that follow the folksonomy principle, which encourages users to create new values that are often undocumented.

While ISO 19157 [6] includes the data quality element known as Quantitative Attribute Accuracy, it lacks a corresponding metric for non-quantitative attributes. This gap suggests a need for a new metric to assess the accuracy of non-quantitative values. However, such a metric should not be integrated into ISO 19157 [6] due to its specific focus. Instead, it should be included in guidelines designed specifically for evaluating OpenStreetMap or folksonomy in general. This approach would allow for better differentiation of situations like *payment:*=**, where the value *only* is correct, yet *yes* might also be considered correct, though with a lower degree of accuracy. Similarly, *outdoor_seating=patio* offers more precise information compared to *outdoor_seating=yes*. Currently, these subtle differences in attribute values cannot be effectively distinguished or described using the data quality elements found in ISO 19157 [6].

OpenStreetMap offers a comprehensive database, but its data quality varies significantly depending on the main tag and geometry type. In our sample data, both attribute and positional accuracy are reasonably good. However, a more significant issue is incompleteness, which includes missing and poorly mapped features and attributes. It is important to note that only a small subset of the database has been evaluated. The overall accuracy and completeness can vary significantly around the world, as demonstrated by numerous studies [9, 2, 10, 11]. This research aimed to evaluate the area of Brno while also exploring how ISO 19157 [6] can be used to assess OpenStreetMap. Yet, it seems that ISO

19157 can not be fully utilized for assessing folksonomy attributes. On the other hand, there is no problem with evaluating metrics like positional accuracy. Comparing Brno with a rural area or a similarly sized city in another country would yield valuable insights. However, this type of evaluation is very time-consuming due to the demands of data collection and processing. It is unlikely that a similar analysis could be conducted over a larger area, as it would require substantial resources. Nonetheless, this smaller-scale analysis offers important insights into the quality of OpenStreetMap data. The uniqueness of this study is underscored by the fact that similar research efforts focusing specifically on attribute evaluation in OpenStreetMap have not yet been conducted, mainly because of the demanding data collection. Previous studies have primarily focused on intrinsic data quality evaluations [1-5] or employed reference datasets that are not fully suitable for assessing attributes within OpenStreetMap [12].

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